

Spacetime and Indivisible Stochastic Quantum Mechanics

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It is possible to provide a real, local, 4D spacetime account for why the *indivisible stochastic* transition matrix reformulation of orthodox quantum mechanics (ISQM) cannot provide a time evolution function for the real particle trajectories. Indivisibility of the transition matrix in a spacetime cobordism region can thus be explained, provided the topology of spacetime in local regions is non-trivial. This motivates revisiting a small neglected body of work from the mid 1990's which we refer to as *topological 4-geon theory* (T4G).

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I. INTRODUCTION

In the Indivisible Stochastic Quantum Mechanics (ISQM) framework a classical-like configuration space is presumed. The dynamics are explicitly non-deterministic and governed by an indivisible (and hence non-Markov) transition matrix [1, 2]. Two criticisms of this framework are that; (i) it can be considered as merely another interpretation of quantum mechanics (QM); and (ii) there is no ontology justifying taking the indivisible stochastic dynamics as a fundamental feature of reality (why not just keep using the wavefunction?) However, ISQM offers several conceptual advantages over other frameworks for thinking about QM, which we will discuss briefly for motivation, and this invites effort to find an ontology that is radically conservative, or minimalist, and explains why the transition probabilities have to be stochastic, even while the elementary particles follow real spacetime trajectories.

We have found such an ontology, known as Topological 4-Geon theory (T4G) that can provide an account of the indivisible dynamics and much more. This is *not* the topological geon proposed by Wheeler [3]. T4G is 4-dimensional, local and real, and yet has an embedded measurement theory (a sub-theory) that satisfies quantum logic (the logic of measurement propositions). Although Wheeler's geometrodynamics is a precursor for T4G theory, so was the particle problem addressed by Einstein and Rosen [4], but the quantum theory derived from these ideas more fairly dates from the work

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of Hadley [5]. It is plausible T4G also can account for the algebraic structure of the Standard Model of particle physics, hints come from at least two independent directions of study [6–8].

We adopt a radically minimalist analysis, following the program currently underway being run by Neil Turok and Latham Boyle. For our present purposes this means we are not allowed any ontology but 4D spacetime of Einstein. This is a deliberate self-imposed constraint, not yet an ontological commitment. We do not claim all there is to reality is spacetime, far from it, our conscious subjective qualia arises from who knows what, but it is likely not from quantum physics. We say this because our radical minimalism implies we can take the “static” 4D Block Universe seriously. Hence there is no physical “flow of time” and no “life”. Yet such experiences are real and *life* is obvious to everyone who thinks. Thus we arrive at a kind of apophatic metaphysics, we just cannot comment at all — as physicists — on the nature of minds and consciousness.

The bulk of this paper after introducing ISQM in §II is devoted to a mostly pedagogical overview of T4G theory. The aim of this paper is only to account for indivisibility in ISQM, but T4G theory is not well known, and so we will endeavour to make a simplified but mostly self-contained seminal presentation of T4G theory, with justifications but without rigorous proofs of results.

There is another reason for providing this seminal preview of T4G, which is that we need a lot more research effort devoted to T4G theory, as there is no community at all devoted to the topic yet. It is such a promising road to explore, even if only for pure applied mathematical pleasure, that we hope the absence of proofs will spur young physicists to take up the challenge of filling in such gaps in the presentation. The point also being that one well-known proof of a result tends to kill attempts to explore other angles of attack, and hence the immaturity of T4G theory offers a wide open playing field which should not be solely ours to enjoy.

II. THE ISQM FRAMEWORK

II.A. Spacetime view of indivisible processes

We define a *classical spacetime cobordism region* to be topologically a time parameterized section of all the (abstract) classical possible paths from one closed compact 3-boundary (the past boundary) to another (the future boundary), including the generalization to curved spacetime. These are closed bounded submanifolds of 4D spacetime. All four concepts are indispensable in this definition — closed, bounded, spacetime, cobordism region — but now that they have been given, for the remainder of this paper we will use the shorthand of simply ‘spacetime cobordism’ or even more abbreviated ‘ST-cobordism’ to refer to this restricted notion. We will introduce only one further generalization later, when we

define a *T4G cobordism*, which is a broader class of submanifolds of spacetime.

In classical general relativity between Cauchy horizons every ST-cobordism is divisible. The proof is standard GR: there is a smooth deterministic time evolution between horizons in GR [9, ch.7].

The notion of classical deterministic evolution between two Cauchy horizons thus has a guaranteed characterization in terms of divisible stochastic processes: for if we do not have all the data from the past Cauchy horizon then we are forced to employ a stochastic time evolution model.

We will not comment upon the exotic cases where even classical mechanics admits singularities and hence non-unique time evolutions. The reader may regard such fringe cases as requiring irreducibly stochastic variables, but such physical circumstances cannot enforce a full universal quantum theory in our opinion.

In stochastic processes *divisibility* refers to the property that a transition matrix at a later time can be decomposed into intermediate transition matrices at earlier times. If Γ is a transition matrix (using dimension $N \rightarrow \infty$ for number of states N , for the continuum state space approximation), then *divisibility* amounts to existence of a Markov matrix $\Gamma(t \leftarrow t_0)$,

$$\Gamma(t) = \Gamma(t \leftarrow t_0)\Gamma(t_0). \quad (1)$$

The Markov condition, for our purposes, is the condition the transition matrices are all unistochastic [10–12].

Assuming an underlying classical configuration space, and a particle ontology (which could be at this stage point-like undefined entities labelled by quantum numbers, or strings, or similar) then Barandes has shown one additional relaxation of classical mechanics is needed to yield ‘textbook’ quantum mechanics. This relaxation is:

1. The unistochastic transition matrices are generically *indivisible*.

Indivisibility just means not divisible:

$$\Gamma(t) \neq \Gamma(t \leftarrow t_0)\Gamma(t_0). \quad (2)$$

See [1, 2, 13]. This is remarkably the only quantum postulate in Barandes’ framework (although as T4G advocates we would say the particle postulate is the *essential* quantum postulate, since — as we hope to show in due course — it is the particle postulate suitably refined which is the ‘cause’ of indivisibility.¹

Critics have pointed out this, “does not buy us anything.” We think such criticism is misplaced. There is a conceptual clarity gained in noting all of orthodox QM can be reformulated as generically indivisible stochastic

¹ We use the term ‘cause’ here minimally, meaning just an “account of” a phenomenon. That is to say, a logically coherent scientific narrative.

processes. The main clarifying concept in our present paper's view is that we can enjoy all of known quantum mechanics in 4D spacetime. Hilbert space and Schrödinger–Dirac spinor time evolution (or path integral sum-over-histories) is relegated to a set of accounting tools for deterministic time evolution of statistical variables. We will have more to say about why this is so later.

The missing fundamental theory is to account for the indivisible processes.

This is a challenge because the indivisibility is non-negotiable. Barandes points out that we only obtain quantum mechanics (entanglement, superposition, interference) if the spacetime dynamics is indivisible. When a ST-cobordism is divisible the time evolution is classical (no interference is possible).

If we think of the evolution of matter fields in general relativity as a Markovian process, then in the region between two Cauchy horizons, the evolution should be composable — meaning that for any intermediate times we can write the evolution as a composition of two earlier stochastic evolutions. This aligns with the classical picture of global hyperbolicity, where a well-posed initial value problem exists, ensuring a deterministic evolution between the horizons.

II.B. Interference and entanglement

In the ISQM framework interference is equivalent to the failure of divisibility. This can be precisely formulated, the interference terms in orthodox QM are exactly the difference between the transition matrix $\Gamma(t)$ at present time t and the *would be* matrix developed from $t_0 < t$. That is,

$$\Gamma(t) - \Gamma(t \leftarrow t_0)\Gamma(t_0)$$

captures interference precisely [1, sec.D].

II.B.1. Entanglement of subsystems

Entanglement is similarly related to failure of divisibility. We need to consider two systems, \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} . We wish to pause to note that later when considering T4G theory we will regard entanglement in more realist terms, not statistical terms, but here in ISQM context we will lay out the weaker *statistical account* for entanglement.

We say entanglement is absent if there is no non-local coupling between subsystems, in which case the composite system transition matrix can be factorized,

$$\text{(Unentangled)} : \Gamma^{\mathcal{AB}}(t) = \Gamma^{\mathcal{A}}(t) \otimes \Gamma^{\mathcal{B}}(t).$$

If there is isotropic spin coupling (fermions or bosons) then the system is entangled, and fails to factorize:

$$\text{(Entangled)} : \Gamma^{\mathcal{AB}}(t) \neq \Gamma^{\mathcal{A}}(t) \otimes \Gamma^{\mathcal{B}}(t).$$

The difference is a measure of the entanglement entropy:

$$e^{S_{\text{ep}}r} \propto \Gamma^{\mathcal{AB}}(t) - \Gamma^{\mathcal{A}}(t) \otimes \Gamma^{\mathcal{B}}(t).$$

This is a statistical account, it leaves ontology of entanglement in a spacetime theory unexplained. However, what ISQM reveals is that entanglement is *logically* inseparable from indivisibility. (Which is a clue for the underlying spacetime physics.) Howso?

The reason is that if the two subsystems are not coupled then each evolves relative to the other classically, hence divisibly — when considered as wholes,

$$\Gamma^{\mathcal{AB}}(t \leftarrow t_0) = \Gamma^{\mathcal{A}}(t \leftarrow t_0) \otimes \Gamma^{\mathcal{B}}(t \leftarrow t_0)$$

which is to say, the internal dynamics in each subsystem can of course exhibit interference and other quantum effects, but as a pair of systems \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} they are relatively classical. Thus if the systems undergo a division event (such as a measurement process that decouples them) then the transition matrix will now compose divisibly,

$$\Gamma^{\mathcal{AB}}(t) = \Gamma^{\mathcal{AB}}(t \leftarrow t_0)\Gamma^{\mathcal{AB}}(t_0).$$

Of further note in ISQM analysis is the Bell-Aspect/EPR class of experiments. The question is posed, how can a classical configuration space provide an account for the violation of Bell Inequalities? Barandes points out that a critical but often glossed-over assumption in deriving Bell Inequalities is the Principle of Reichenbach common causes. That is, if two events A and B have correlated marginal probabilities then there is a common cause C . Or equivalently, Reichenbach says if the joint probability $P(A \cap B)$ fails to factorize $P(A \cap B) \neq P(A)P(B)$, then there must be a common cause C guaranteeing a factorization,

$$P(A \cap B|C) = P(A|C)P(B|C).$$

However, this is not strictly a necessary assumption when the spacetime cobordism is indivisible.

Unruh [14] noted this in a 2002 paper, pointing out (in Barandes' paraphrasing) "*a formulation of QM that fails to adhere to the strictures of Reichenbach's principle of common causes could violate Bell's principle of local causality without necessarily entailing nonlocal causation.*"

The critical thing to note here relevant to spacetime physics is that the key assumption made by J.S. Bell is that one can integrate or sum-over variables representing the presumed common cause C . If we are not permitted by physical laws to sum-over such variables in a quantum theory then Reichenbach's Principle fails for QM and Bell cannot derive his inequalities.

As far as we are aware Barandes does not provide a physical motive for why Reichenbach's Principle might fail in the 'quantum regime', except for noting indivisible stochastic processes are counter-intuitive and may not adhere to Reichenbach's Principle for all possible events A and B . We think this is correct and we can motivate this in T4G context.

Barandes[1] also discusses decoherence, non-locality, and the measurement process in ISQM terms, which we will skip, since the T4G theory which we turn to now has a compatible but, we think, more fundamental account of these phenomena.

II.B.2. Particle self-entanglement

At this stage we introduce the notion that elementary particles can be self-entangled, and this can explain — or statistically account for — single particle interference.

While a general proof of the principle is not yet forthcoming, there are three robust results that suggest entanglement and interference are essentially the same phenomena (seen in different contexts).

1. Two-slit interference.[15]
2. Quantum circuits.[16]
3. Generalized probability theories (GPTs).[17]

A few comments can be made while avoiding an extensive review of these results.

As preface, we need to note that it has been claimed interference can occur without entanglement. Three cases are considered. (i) single particle interference (the Two-Slit paradigm). (ii) multiphoton non-local quantum interference.[18] (iii) algorithmic quantum search without entanglement.[19]

Each of these counter-examples however do not work. For (i), two-slit interference has a natural explanation in terms of entanglement, which we will remark upon next. For (ii), we cannot explain any non-locality in spacetime physics without wormhole-like topology, which is a form of entanglement, even if via vacuum states and undetected photons, so the “interference without entanglement” is not really a demonstration that entanglement is not essential. Those experiments demonstrate only that the photons one detects can display interference effects without each being entangled with the others. However, each photon must still be self-entangled, as in the Two-Slit experiment case, for otherwise there is no interference. For (iii) we can agree that wave-particles used to probe the database in the entanglement-free algorithm are not entangled with any other particle. However, this misses the point that interference of a single particle cannot occur without self-entanglement. The article by Lloyd [19] was written before GPTs were known, so could be forgiven for failing to realize all single-particle interference is equivalent to entanglement (between the two paths).

Moreover, we reject the wave-particle duality in any case. With ISQM the “wave nature” is revealed to be fictional, or what we prefer to think of as *an accounting tool*. The supposedly entanglement-free quantum search

algorithm exploits the wave properties. In ISQM context this implies indivisibility and hence entanglement.

What is unknown is the nature of this type of self-entanglement. Given we lack a spacetime geometric picture the concept is not well-defined yet. In most practical examples the “self-entanglement” can be construed still as entanglement of the particle with other particles that comprise the measurement apparatus. This is possible in an ISQM and T4G account (still to come) because we presume the physical configuration space is real, and the wavefunction is a fiction. So we have no Wigner’s Friend of a Friend type concerns. The measurement devices actually exist classically and are never proverbial Schrödinger Cats.

Entanglement implies a bipartite structure, since just at the most minimal statistical level entanglement is characterized by failure of the bipartite system to factorize. Or in other words, information describing the system is non-local or shared. There are at least two ways this could occur in spacetime physics. One is that the elementary particles could be themselves wormhole-like structures (or multi-wormhole structures). Another is that the vacuum is riddled with wormholes, and so particle dynamics is sensitive to non-local effects arising from the vacuum topology.

Both types of entanglement (of the particle itself, internal ER-bridges, or via the conjectured ambient vacuum “foamy spacetime” topology) could be physical, so could play a role in explaining the interference effects. But this is getting ahead of ourselves and already introducing T4G concepts. Bookmarking these comments for now, we return to the two-slit interference case.

a. Two-slit interference We’ve implicated Two-Slit interference twice now. It is perhaps the important case, since it is quite universal. The general two-slit phenomenon is in play for any interference of multiple paths. With the failure to detect significant exotic path interference in Three-Slit experiments[20–22], the current consensus is that all m -way interference can be reduced to two-way interference.

O’Hara showed how two-slit interference can be analyzed in terms of isotropic spin-coupled states, which is exactly a form of entanglement.[15]

In this analysis, which is compatible with particle physics models like ISQM and T4G, the elementary particle gets entangled with the matter at the apertures. No waves in Hilbert space superposed then recombined are needed. It is an entirely particle account. Particles, but which are entangled.

b. Quantum Circuits Interference in quantum circuits is only observed when two possible histories are ‘recombined’. This recombination is a semantically loaded term. There need be no actual paths or physical waves that get combined in superposition, since the wavefunction description is only a statistical account, it is not causal, and can be viewed in pure information-theoretic terms. Which is to say, in non-physical terms.

The challenge of completing QM for a *minimalist*

minded realist is to provide a physical spacetime account of these phenomena.

The point to be made here is that without entanglement of the abstract histories (the two possible paths say, in an interferometer or quantum circuit) we do not observe interference. Huang *et al* call this “entanglement–interference complementarity” [16]. This appears to align well with T4G and ISQM, since the complementary interference occurs when the particle is entangled with a *which-way path detector*, which is more or less exactly the type of situation O’Hara considers [15]. The question is whether entanglement is more than raw unexplained statistical correlation. This is not answered by the Quantum Information sciences.

c. GPT Frameworks Similar conclusions have been reached in the context of Generalized Probability Theories (GPTs). [23] In particular see Aubrun et al., [17] for a precise statement and proof of the result:

“Entanglement and superposition are equivalent concepts in any physical theory.”

II.C. Note on statistical accounts

Notice that these ISQM accounts for interference and entanglement are statistical accounts. There is no notion of metaphysical causality involved. This is what makes ISQM uncontroversial. One can hardly quibble with a statistical account, since no strong ontological claims are being made. At most weak and indirect ontological claims are inferred: the configuration space is essentially “classical” in ISQM and accommodates a 4D spacetime ontology of *some unspecified kind*, although that is modulo finer Planck scale spacetime structure. Hence, although the configuration space is classical the unspecified variety of spacetime dynamics and kinematics (the time evolution) is non-classical, precisely because it is indivisible.

This is why we have used the word “account” in the previous review, rather than “explain” or “cause of”. Statistical accounts in our view are not causal accounts. Without wishing to make a big fuss of it, we also personally urge scientists to be careful about *causal language*, because in our opinion physics has no proper concept of causality. What physics provides is explanation, not causation.

A second note here might be helpful. We placed “classical” in quote marks above referring to the ISQM configuration space because in our view (the T4G view) the particle postulate *is* the *quantum postulate*. Thus once we say there are particles (local compact regions of non-trivial spacetime topology) then we are already beyond classical mechanics. The configuration space is however still classical-like if we take a point-particle approximation. This is a matter of suitability for purposes of convenience, sometimes the point-like particle is sufficient, however T4G is really a *stringy theory*.

Further features of ISQM are interesting but not important for the remainder of our paper and so will not be discussed in this brief review.

The puzzle remains, for any aspiring minimalist realist, how can events in a real spacetime cobordism region possibly be indivisible?

This question provides a good motivation for taking a new look at an old idea that was advanced around 1996 in a PhD Thesis out of the University of Warwick. This was the ER=EPR idea, but about 20 years before that slogan was coined by Juan Maldacena in a completely different context (of black hole information loss).

III. TOPOLOGICAL 4-GEON THEORY

T4G theory began with the work of Mark Hadley at Warwick in the mid 1990’s. [5, 24, 25] The basic idea is remarkably simple and surprisingly fruitful. It is the proposal that most features of quantum mechanics and particle phenomenology arise from “wormhole topology”. We use this phrase somewhat advisedly, it is not intended to conjure up images of connected black holes and time-machines. The “wormholes” associated with T4G are minimal, or “Planckian”, and cannot be traversed by bulk matter.

When we use the word ‘Planckian’ we mean the wormhole structures are discernable only around the Planck scale, but not that the topology is local. Wormholes are highly non-local structures, the ends of an ER-bridge can be arbitrarily far apart in spacetime.

We would also like to note we are using the word ‘wormhole’ loosely. There are a rich variety of non-trivial topological structures supported within the framework of 4D general relativity. The sub-set of such structures which yield indivisible ST-cobordisms are what account for quantum mechanics. But there could be further rich wormhole-like structure. Thus ‘wormhole’ in our paper just means ‘non-trivial local compact topology’ but path connected in 4D spacetime.

When we wish to emphasise this topological variety we will use the phrase ‘wormhole-like’.

Another subtlety is that we aim to stay close to GR. This means just because one can find a 4D wormhole-rich geometry does not make it physical or stable. The elementary particles must satisfy the symmetries of the Standard Model, which via the invariants thereof we will take as our ersatz for stability.

At this stage we should note this is a wide open problem. What local compact topology does GR admit that is stable only around the Planck scale — with permitted wormhole connections at any scale — and which transform one to another in representations of the groups of the Standard Model?

The only mainstream theoretical research that is closely related to T4G is the Holographic conjecture of Susskind and Maldacena which they captured in the pithy koan ER=EPR. [26, 27] Which just means entan-

lement and Einstein-Rosen bridge structure are dual. That is, they are the same phenomena but placed in different theoretical framework context. ER-bridges in General Relativity (GR) and EPR in quantum mechanics (QM). More recently Susskind extended this conjecture to a more far-reaching koan he dubbed QM=GR.[28] However, this was always in the unphysical context of String theories and AdS/CFT.

T4G is a stringy sort of theory, but grounded in 4D spacetime. The wormhole-like Planck scale topology is the “string.”

III.A. GR with Non-trivial spacetime topology

A topological 4-geon is tricky to define precisely, but fairly intuitive. It is easiest to define a *partial* 4-geon, which is any region of ambient (asymptotically Minkowski topology, or equivalently Ricci-flat) spacetime containing non-trivial topology which is not further decomposable into subregions. The latter constraint just means the topology is minimal.

An entire 4-geon includes spacetime connected components via minimal Einstein-Rosen bridges (ER-bridges).

A minimal ER-bridge is any spacetime wormhole (of some signature or another) that has one Planck unit of area cross section, so has minimum entropy and cannot Hawking evaporate.

A T4G-cobordism is a cobordism triple $(\mathcal{M}, \partial M_1, \partial M_2)$ where the 4-manifold \mathcal{M} is pseudo-Riemannian, the boundaries ∂M_1 and ∂M_2 have spacelike separated structures, and the interior can be characterized by a time-like parameter t , all the 3-space structure on one boundary ∂M_i having the time parameter t_i . We refer (for convenience) to the interior of the ST-cobordism as a topological cylinder, or just ‘the cylinder’.

This is so far just a curved spacetime ST-cobordism, and (ignoring the elementary particle ‘defects’) topologically is exactly a 4-cylinder. The T4G cobordism is not going to be generically necessarily a cylinder, but we can define a T4G-cobordism easier if we use the ST-cylinder imagery.

A *T4G-cobordism* has two additional possible structures:

- (i) ER-bridges may connect the interior to regions of spacetime external to *the ST-cylinder*.
- (ii) The interior of the cylinder has non-trivial topology, which is just to say, (a) 4-geons propagate from ∂M_1 to ∂M_2 , and (b) an ER-bridge or any wormhole-like structure might exist entirely inside the cylinder.

The subtlety that the 3-boundary ∂M_2 need not be connected will be something we will not be needing to worry about in the present paper, but clearly the reason one may need to “draw” the ∂M_2 boundary in an unusual way is to keep track of 4-geons that tunnel out of the

ST-cylinder region. It is a moot point, since no one is ever likely to have the microscope to track a 4-geon, we just need the unitarity and the statistical account to preserve currents.

All we will need to stipulate is that a *measurement* takes place via position measurements on the ∂M_2 boundary (or in practice at least two nearby in time boundaries — a trivial enough subtlety).

T4G theory in this minimal model is only mathematical and is not physical without additional symmetry constraints on the allowed 4-geon structures. Without defining these structures (because we cannot yet do so) we assume the algebra for the symmetries between these 4-geon structures is the algebra of the Standard Model. While we cannot yet define these 4-geon structures as spacetime topology, the existence of such structure is highly plausible. This is not a wild conjecture, because the generators for all the unitary groups of the Standard Model exist in the Clifford Spacetime Algebra (STA).[6]

T4G theory has just one quantum postulate, which is,

1. The elementary particles are all 4-geons.

Because Standard Model particles are described by symmetry group representations in an abstract space, they are not easy to classify as 4-geons. No one to our knowledge has even proposed any such classification, so this is a good open problem.

III.A.1. Towards a T4G Algebra

One nice feature of T4G theory is that the STA naturally lends itself to T4G modelling. In STA the Standard Model spinors are simply transformation instructions, which can be decomposed into three parts,

$$\psi = \sqrt{\rho} e^{I\beta} R \quad (3)$$

a dilation $\sqrt{\rho}$ (scaling); a boost and/or space rotation rotor, R , and an antiparticle duality ‘rotation’ mixing factor $e^{I\beta}$. Here $I = e_0 e_1 e_2 e_3$ is the spacetime pseudoscalar (a real unit 4-volume element) which squares to -1 . The frame $\{e_\mu\}$ vectors are a local fiducial frame (laboratory frame) for GR and STA quantum mechanics (STA-QM).

The rotor part can be composite, so includes all internal rotations and boosts. The spinor itself in the STA transforms under Lorentz rotations from the left, $\psi \rightarrow L\psi$, and under ‘internal’ unitary rotations on the right, $\psi \rightarrow \psi R$. The characteristic of a spinor is that it has this half-rotation instruction, since a full transform by ψ on a multivector observable A is given by a sandwich product, $\psi A \tilde{\psi}$, where $\tilde{\psi}$ is the *reverse* of ψ .

The STA-QM theory is deterministic, meaning that the evolution of the spinor is given by solutions of classical equations of motion, which do not support entanglement, hence cannot provide effective statistical superposition. In STA the quantum theory is obtained by

admitting entanglement, and hence stochastic superposition. As in ISQM, the wave-like behaviour of the stringy or point-like particles is completely accounted for in the indivisible stochastic dynamics governing transitions in a time-evolution story. Planck’s constant enters this story via the commutation relations for the algebra of the STA bivectors and pseudoscalar, where it is set to the natural value $\hbar = 1$. Any other value is just reparametrization, so without physical meaning. In this framework then, \hbar is essentially topological.

One other little great advantage of this framework for QM is that all probability is Kolmogorov, and contained in the \mathbb{R} valued factor $\sqrt{\rho}$ in the spinor. The \mathbb{C} structure is all in the rotors and the duality transform. Unlike orthodox QM, this STA approach reveals not one, but several \mathbb{C} structures, allowing the theoretician to discriminate between them, and thus geometrize QM more than normally presented.

To ease pedagogical transition we recommend thinking of probabilities as Kolmogorov, and moving the “weirdness” of quantum amplitudes to how you conceive of particle dynamics, not how one conceives of the mathematical subject of probability theory. Thus, in T4G, probability is neither ‘classical’ nor ‘quantum’, it is just mathematical, it is an abstract mathematical concept which people think in terms of — whether frequentist or Bayesian — not a physical concept *per se*.

Any *deterministic* time evolution equations for this ψ are inherently probabilistic, and hence overall such a theory is nondeterministic. However, the theory is only non-deterministic in *time evolution*, not in any deeper meta-physical sense except at spacetime boundaries.

Also, except for exceptionally simple nearly closed systems, the deterministic time evolution for ψ should eventually break down as memory effects become important and the data from the past Cauchy boundary no longer provide all the data for the time evolution, in other words, when a Bayesian update of the transition probabilities is required. We see this as a physical and dynamical process mostly due to the fact no system in nature is ever truly closed, and hence always requires more variables to be accurately described than are available on the past Cauchy boundary.

This is in accord with ISQM, where one models QM as time evolved transition probabilities. Classicality results when the Γ are divisible, and QM results if the Γ are indivisible. Most measurements entail unavoidable *division events* in Barandes’ terminology, these are essentially decouplings, and a system will only evolve indivisibly with the environment thereafter once there is a new interaction. We point out interactions are impossible to avoid, and so all systems will be indivisible to some degree. How “quantum” they are will depend on what we choose to observe, however this is not a mystical observer dependent reality, it is simply pragmatic. We know the spacetime cobordism underlying ISQM is almost everywhere indivisible, but the entanglement thereby implied is not necessarily going to implicate the measurement outcomes

if we are performing measurements that are not sensitive to the entanglement/indivisibility.

To finish the STA definitions, we have the basis vector products and the metric signature,

$$e_0^2 = e_0 \cdot e_0 = -1, \quad e_i^2 = +1 \quad (i \neq 0)$$

and $e_\mu e_\nu = e_\mu \cdot e_\nu + e_\mu \wedge e_\nu = e_\mu \wedge e_\nu$ for $\mu \neq \nu$. We usually abbreviate these *bivectors* (outer products of vectors) using combined subscripts $e_\mu \wedge \nu = e_{\mu\nu}$. These subscripts are labels for the vectors, they are not coordinate indices. In general the main reason one uses Clifford algebra is to conduct analysis entirely coordinate-free.

The anti-symmetric wedge product (or outer product) $a \wedge b = -b \wedge a$ of two vectors is defined in terms of the graded geometric product,

$$a \wedge b = \frac{1}{2}(ab - ba)$$

and the inner product, e.g., $e_\mu \cdot e_\nu$ are similarly defined,

$$a \cdot b = \frac{1}{2}(ab + ba).$$

The full geometric product (for vectors) is the fundamental algebraic product for a mixed-grade Clifford algebra,

$$ab = a \cdot b + a \wedge b.$$

A lot of linear algebra, or multivector algebra can be simplified using a grade-projection operation, which projects out the single grade components of a multivector:

$$\langle M \rangle_k = k\text{-grade parts of } M.$$

The use of bra-ket parentheses for grade projection is not just incidental, since the scalar-part $\langle \psi \phi \rangle_0$ for the geometric product of two spinors is closely related to the QM overlap or inner product. Mathematically-physically (which is to say in the present context, *as a model for measurement processes*) these are also projections.

In T4G as in STA quantum mechanics (and classical mechanics) each point in spacetime has a frame $\{e_\mu\}$. This is simply how we *model* spacetime. The “mother algebra” is the full 16-dimensional STA, with a unit scalar, 4 vectors, 6 bivectors, 4 trivectors and the pseudoscalar. The algebra subsumes the algebra of n -forms for spacetime and the entire theory of determinants for the associated linear algebra. (See [29] for a terse but fairly comprehensive treatment of multivector calculus and differential geometry using Clifford algebra.)

Several natural *real* “complex” structures² are apparent in this STA formulation of spinor theory, and all of them have simple *real* spacetime geometric meaning. First the scalars and pseudoscalar I give a “complex”

² We do not think in terms of complex analysis in T4G theory. All the holomorphic structure in spacetime physics is *real-valued* bivector structure.

structure, with $I^2 = -1$ the role of the unit imaginary squared. Also each space rotation and each boost is generated by a bivector, either spacelike e_{ij} or timelike e_{0i} , $i, j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. Here the unit bivectors are,

$$B_{\mu\nu} = e_\mu \wedge e_\nu$$

Each bivector specifies a plane of rotation (the (e_μ, e_ν) plane) and has a natural holomorphic structure generated by the unit scalar and the bivector. For example, one \mathbb{C} structure from e_{12} is the minimal even sub-algebra generated by $\{1, e_{12}\}$, which is the algebra of the 2D xy plane in usual labelling conventions. You can verify all the unit spacelike bivectors are roots of -1 , $e_{ij}^2 = (e_i \wedge e_j)^2 = -1$.

The timelike bivectors generate boosts and square to $+1$, with the unit time oriented vector $e_0^2 = -1$, thus

$$e_{03}^2 = (e_0 e_3)(e_0 e_3) = -e_0 e_0 e_3 e_3 = +e_3^2 = +1.$$

To boost or rotate *any* multivector M the STA uses the same sandwich product regardless of the generator:

$$M \rightarrow M' = R M \tilde{R}$$

where if the unit bivector generator is $B = e_{\mu\nu}$, the rotors here are,

$$R = e^{-B\theta/2} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{R} = e^{B\theta/2}.$$

The only difference is for rotations θ is the angle, while for boosts θ is the *rapidity*, more often denoted $\alpha = \tanh^{-1} \beta$.

Shortly we will note the Dirac spinor is a more fundamental object in classical general relativity than the metric, towards emphasizing this point we can remark that the rotors R transform single-sided under a general rotation, that is, if $R_b = R(B)$ is any rotation with a bivector generator B , then another rotor say R_a will transform as,

$$R_a \rightarrow R'_a = R_b R_a.$$

which is easily proven using the fact rotors compose double-sided, in other words, the result on a multivector M of two rotations, one say R_a and another defined by R_b , is,

$$M \rightarrow M' = R_a R_b M \tilde{R}_b \tilde{R}_a.$$

This leads straight forward to the result the spacetime rotors are unit ‘fermions’. The rotors are the elements of the even sub-algebra of spacetime not including the pseudoscalar — that is to say, the scalars and bivectors. What we mean by ‘fermion’ here is not the full Dirac spinor form, but just the rotor part of the spinor. We certainly do *not* mean a physical particle or real field. The field defined by the rotors taking values at each spacetime position is a way of defining a transformation instruction on the algebra of observables, not a way of describing an elementary particle or string. In any case, the “fermionic”

result is easily seen by writing the effect of a 2π rotation on a general composite rotor $R = R_a R_b$.

Fixing R_a for example, we can ask what the effect on R is if R_b is the instruction for a rotation by 2π :

$$R \rightarrow e^{-B2\pi/2} R_a = e^{-B\pi} R_a = -R_a.$$

Any vector, \vec{v} here would have taken a 2π excursion returning to itself, $v \rightarrow R_b v \tilde{R}_b$, but evidently the rotor R itself has effectively been rotated through π , although this is loose language. Rotors are transformation instructions of mixed grade (generally) and do not thus represent any physical object, so we should only say they *get transformed singled-sided*, hence in the 2π case by a sign change.

For the full rotation by $R = R_a R_b$ the vector v does what we expect, $v \rightarrow R_a R_b v \tilde{R}_b \tilde{R}_a = R_a v \tilde{R}_a$. This reflects nothing but the fact the rotors double-cover the rotations, since R and $-R$ describe the same rotation, but do so using opposite handedness. This implies rotors are the natural real geometric transforms underpinning the special unitary groups in the representation theory side of quantum mechanics, at least this is what one can say in a minimalist T4G framework.

The Clifford frame $\{e_\mu\}$ replaces (and greatly simplifies) the tetrad or vierbein in the STA for gravity, and gravity is formulated as a theory which gauges space-time position relabelling invariance and rotation invariance. This is known as Gauge Gravity (GG, or sometimes GTG) [30]. Optionally one can naturally extend this Gauged Gravity to conformal gravity[31] with scale invariance gauging as well — which is useful in cosmology.

This Gauge Gravity theory is a reformulation of GR, it is a classical theory and is unrelated to AdS/CFT and is not a Yang-Mills (graviton) theory, yet most naturally GG incorporates spinors too, which are the form of matter fields from which the GG Lagrangian is most conveniently derived, starting from the Dirac Equation. In this formulation of GR there are subtle differences with Einstein-Hilbert gravity at horizons [30], which is an interesting research avenue worth pursuing, but not of interest to us at present.

III.A.2. What about the graviton?

In this paper we will not dwell too much longer on Gauge Gravity, but it is an important part of our story, because the T4G cobordism is *all gravity and only gravity*, so-to-speak. There are a few important remarks to be made for setting the context of our later attempt to find ISQM in T4G theory.

We have no need to introduce gravitons any-more. In the STA-QM the graviton field was only like a boson, it was an instruction for a transformation. With GG theory there is no longer a need for these fields, they would be redundant, so to include graviton degrees of freedom invites the pathologies such as UV divergences that are

well-known. However, T4G theory could admit gravity wave instantons or solitons, which when entangled would act a lot like gravitons. It is an empirical question to worry about whether such fields need to be accounted for in the full Lagrangian for the SM + Gravity.

This may beg the question what happens to the CPT-Symmetric LR-Symmetric Standard Model and the curing of the vacuum energy and Weyl anomalies? [32] At this stage we are not entirely sure. On first inspection though, there does not seem to be a need for the graviton in the CPT-Symmetric SM approach. We think the “radically minimalist” program of Turok & Boyle and their collaborators will work without the graviton. We think it may even simplify, because now, in T4G, we are saying there is no need to sum-over spacetime topologies. Why not?

It is because the elementary particles already are the spacetime topology, and the SM path integral is actually performing this sum-over-topologies. To try to perform an extra sum over topologies by supposing the spacetime metric also fluctuates is, in the T4G picture, entirely redundant and pathological.

We will however revisit the graviton shortly after setting up more spacetime algebra basics. With or without a quantized metric, the *concept* of the graviton must still be dealt with, because in T4G gravity is still a gauge theory.

We will jump ahead then to the particle physics. We’ve extended the discussion above just to point out this jump to particle physics is not really a jump, it is still gravity theory, we are just zooming into Planck scale spacetime topology.

Except that now all the elementary particles are elements of 4D spacetime, there are no abstract fibre bundles and no Calabi–Yau dimensions. It all takes place in a gravitational context, albeit highly non-classical due to the non-trivial local topology. The gauge fibres can of course be reintroduced at any time for purposes of analysis, but one no longer needs to think of them as fundamental ontology, they are, like the concept of a Lagrangian or Action, just accounting tools we need or conveniently use to write down time evolution equations of motion.

We now pick-up from where we diverted from, which was the Clifford spacetime algebra, now in the context of QM.

III.B. Spinors in the STA

Our only goal in this lightning review is to point out the Dirac, Majorana and Weyl spinors all have representations in the even subalgebra of the STA, denoted $Cl^+(3, 1)$.

To represent the Paul algebra in the STA we use the convenient concept of *relative* vectors, these are actually spacetime bivectors, but they form a representation of euclidean 3-space in a co-moving frame with a fixed

timelike basis vector e_0 . The three Pauli basis vectors are,

$$\sigma_i = e_i e_0$$

it is a simple exercise to verify these satisfy the Pauli algebra. Although they are bivectors, relative to the time direction chosen by e_0 they act as 3-space vectors, and can be taken as a basis for the geometric algebra of 3-space. (Together with the pseudoscalar they provide the generators for $u(1)$ and $su(2)$.)

The idea is that the 3-space defined by the $\{\sigma_i\}$ are special, they are a basis for the *relative space* of an elementary particle which has a co-moving velocity in the e_0 direction.

There is a simple dictionary translation from Hilbert space spinors to STA spinors. For the Pauli spinors, for example:

$$|\psi\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} a^0 + ia^3 \\ -a^2 + ia^1 \end{pmatrix} \longleftrightarrow \psi = a^0 + a^k I\sigma_k \in Cl^+(3, 1). \quad (4)$$

on the left of this dictionary is the Hilbert space spinor rep. On the right is the STA representation. The Dirac spinors can then be built from the Pauli spinors,

$$\begin{pmatrix} |\psi\rangle \\ |\phi\rangle \end{pmatrix} \longleftrightarrow \psi + \phi\sigma_3.$$

Similar expressions or dictionaries exist for the Weyl and Majorana spinor representations, which are just changes of basis. All the known Standard Model particles are Dirac or Majorana spinors, and so with the gauge generators already expressed in the STA (see [6]) we do not have anything further to add to the claim T4G theory can incorporate the Standard Model, via the STA. We will just repeat for emphasis, because this is an important open problem that would be incredibly rewarding to work upon, the T4G theory does not yet have a topological spacetime account for the spinors, we only have the STA *algebraic* account.

Also, we should note this is not an easy problem to work on, because it involves some element of functoriality. The spinors are not objects of spacetime geometry *per se*. They are dilation + rotation + duality mixing *instructions*. The spinors act on the spacetime multivector observables (the bilinear invariants), and this is why they are so useful in a Measurement Theory like QM, or like ISQM in particular.

However, writing down the *instructions* (i.e., the spinors) for rotating and scaling the observables is not a direct description of spacetime topology. T4G is just conjecturing there is some relation to be found. The enormous advantage of T4G+STA is that this functorial correspondence is greatly simplified because all of the work can be done in the single STA category. This is to say that the topology of our physical spacetime is functorially related to the Clifford spacetime algebra, or that the STA is the simplest *language* for describing spacetime algebraic topology.

III.C. Scalar Projection and Dirac bra-ket

A greatly underappreciated aspect of the Clifford algebra framework is how natural the Dirac bra-ket becomes. We dispense with the Hilbert space and matrix algebra, and use only the geometric algebra. This can be extended to any Clifford algebra for the Standard Model, for example $\mathbb{C}\ell_8$ in our other paper [33], but for simplicity we will stick here to the STA.

As previously mentioned, the spinors ψ are really *just spacetime rotors with two extra factors, one for statistics, another for duality rotation*. From the above correspondence there must then be a dictionary translation from the Dirac bra-ket for expectation values to the Clifford algebra. It is probably not historical accident, but deliberate design, that the early exponents of CA quantum mechanics (Hestenes, Lasenby, et al) use the same angle brackets to denote their scalar projection operation.

$$\langle \psi \rangle = \langle \psi \rangle_0 = \text{scalar part of } \psi.$$

How does this translate to the Hilbert space, \mathcal{H} , Dirac bracket?

The answer is simple but not directly the naïve response. For in the Hilbert space we do take an adjoint, which in the STA (or general Clifford spinor) framework is a reversion $\tilde{\psi}$ (reverse order of geometric products in the components of ψ). This naïve response would yield a real scalar, whereas the general expectation value for an observable would have other grades, for example the spin, which is a bivector plane.

In any case the ψ adjoint product with a spinor ϕ ,

$$\tilde{\psi}\phi$$

is not real scalar valued but in general would have such k -grades, at least $k = 2$ bivectors. However, it is convenient to use the real scalar, $\langle \tilde{\psi}\phi \rangle_0$ in the obvious way, which is to simply note the dictionary identity,

$$\mathcal{H} \ni \text{Re} \langle \psi | \phi \rangle \longleftrightarrow \langle \tilde{\psi}\phi \rangle_0 \in \mathbb{C}\ell_{3,1}^+$$

we then at least have the basic ‘metric’ correspondence,

$$\mathcal{H} \ni \langle \psi | \psi \rangle \longleftrightarrow \langle \tilde{\psi}\psi \rangle \in \mathbb{C}\ell_{3,1}^+$$

since on the right-hand side we have,

$$\langle \tilde{\psi}\psi \rangle = (a^0 - a^k I\sigma_k)(a^0 + a^j I\sigma_j) = a^\mu a^\mu.$$

at least in the STA. Generalization to general $\mathbb{C}\ell_{p,q}$ model can obviously be made once a similar correspondence is set-up with the Standard Model spinors. To extend this to a general inner product bracket, we note on the Hilbert space side,

$$\langle \psi | \phi \rangle = \text{Re} \langle \psi | \phi \rangle - i \text{Re} \langle \psi | i\phi \rangle$$

To obtain the Clifford algebra dictionary translation we identify what multiplication by the unit imaginary is in

the STA, and in the Dirac/Weyl spinor translation this is right-multiplication (geometric product) by the bivector $I\sigma_3$, and so the general transition amplitude is,

$$\langle \psi | \phi \rangle \longleftrightarrow \langle \tilde{\psi}\phi \rangle + \langle \tilde{\psi}\phi I\sigma_3 \rangle I\sigma_3.$$

Where again on the left is the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} and on the right correspondence is the STA Clifford algebra $\mathbb{C}\ell_{3,1}$.

Applications to simple QM and Dirac theory can be found in chapters 9–11 of [34].

* * *

Further review of the spacetime algebra (STA) is unnecessary for this paper, and references may be consulted for those interested [35].

There is a good reason for going to these lengths to give a lightening review of the STA. The reason is the crucial *change in perspective* of how we view the spinors of the Standard Model.

The perspective afforded by this STA reformulation of QM is quite deep, we think, not mathematically, but philosophically for spacetime physics.

III.D. Indivisibility from T4G

Now we come to the crux. We believe that it is essentially the antiparticle duality mixing that encodes in the spinor the essential indivisible stochastic dynamics which is made clear in the ISQM reformulation. (This extends to bosons as well, but it is conceptually easier to talk about the fermions for which we have the convenience of appeal to Dirac Theory.)

Reminding ourselves of our self-imposed minimalist constraints, we find that without allowing ourselves to invoke abstract nonsense like mystical entanglement or ghost-like guiding potentials and Everettian branches, we find there is a unique way to account for ISQM indivisibility in T4G context. It happens to nicely coincide with Turok & Boyle’s ideas in CPT-Symmetric Universe cosmology. We can even invoke a simple phrase and most physicists will immediately comprehend where we are going: we are going to exploit the Stueckelberg trick, only taking it seriously as not a trick.

We regard the antiparticles exactly as time reversed particles. Only in T4G we are also able to help ourselves to some sort of “spacetime realism” (not caring to know what that really means) and so take a 4D Block Universe perspective. It is not necessary to say the particle “gets turned around in time”. That is just a manner of speaking when one is forced to adopt a time evolution story. However, that is physics in a nutshell. Contemplating the 4D Block Universe is for metaphysics. We must tell the time evolution story if we are pretending to be doing science.

To get to indivisibility we need to find what in T4G is truly responsible for the non-Markov processes between two measurement boundaries ∂M_1 and ∂M_2 . The strategy is to,

1. Rule out the dilation and rotor factors.
2. Use the Stueckelberg process to provide the geometrical picture for the spinor duality mixing factor transform $e^{I\beta}$.
3. Abstract the topology for a typical T4G-cobordism containing a Stueckelberg process to show the stochastic description is both necessary and indivisible.

III.D.1. Dilation and Duality Factors

The rotor part R of the STA spinor ψ is clearly a transformation instruction, acting on the STA algebra of observables (which are all defined in terms of the basis vectors $\{e_\mu\}$ and their duals $\{e^\mu\}$). There is nothing directly stochastic about these rotors. This implies all the quantum statistics, or stochastic processes according to ISQM, are encoded in the dilation factor $\sqrt{\rho}$ and the duality transform $e^{I\beta}$.

The dilation factor is the easiest to deal with, because it is a real scalar and so is just the field-like accounting for classical statistical mechanics. Statistical mechanics of a special variety though, because in our spacetime physics we have irreducibly indeterministic dynamics. In other words, we cannot pin the elementary particles down. (Heisenberg’s Uncertainty Principle can be explained in T4G theory, but will take us too far afield in this section, we will remark briefly on it later.)

The field encoded in the spacetime dependence of ρ and R (via the real coefficients in Eq.(4)) is nothing but a probability distribution function. It is quantum by inheritance of the role the spinor plays on the whole theory — chiefly that we find (empirically) we should superpose solutions to the Dirac Equation (or run the whole path integral in the Lagrangian form of QM). Why?

(We will stick to Dirac Theory or QED for our next little discussion, but you can make the appropriate generalizations to the entire Standard Model phenomenology.)

It is not because we cannot find which path the electron takes from ∂M_1 and ∂M_2 , which is also true, rather it is because a photon *from the future* (so-to-speak) interacts topologically with the electron and reverses it in time. This is all in a manner of speaking. Remember, there is no flow of time in T4G theory. There is only time evolution in our necessary account for what we call *physics*.

The question now is why does this lead to indivisibility? Why is it not merely insufficient information and hence classical statistical mechanics?

III.D.2. The indivisibility result

The answer is pretty subtle. We do have to (fortunately) appeal to our minimalist strictures. There is no

way a photon can magically turn the electron around in time. Maybe in uninterpreted QFT you say “there is an amplitude for this”, but under our minimalist strictures that is magical thinking. To appease the QFT aficionados, we realize adding a law-like feature to a theory (in this case Dirac theory) to allow for pair production and annihilation is perfectly fine. In our context though it is not allowed. (Essentially we are making a Bayesian version of an Occam Razor argument — no new laws and structures!).³

In T4G the only way the electron can get “Stueckelberged” is if there is a wormhole it can traverse. The wormhole is of a variety that changes the time orientation. The whole process must respect the local symmetries of standard QFT and so must be gauged. In one way or another the photon is providing this ER-bridge structure, or in combination with vacuum structures. Since the photon is structureless outside of perhaps String Theory, we cannot say much more about this process.

A cartoon diagram is invited here, but we will refrain because it is almost bound to be misleading. One cannot just draw a U-turn on a spacetime diagram and proclaim “see, physics!” As remarked above, we do not have a complete picture of the T4G topology which we are invoking. Ours is still “magical thinking” if you wanted to be a pedantic critic. Far less magical though than other frameworks.

One may also choose to not think of a wormhole traversal ‘turning the electron around’ but rather take the 4D Block Universe view and draw a ‘trouser diagram’ as in string theory or TQFT. The wormhole-like structure is then just part of pre-existing spacetime topology.

String theory is not a bad paradigm to have in mind here. We replace the 2D conformally symmetric string worldsheet with actual 4D spacetime. (From public comments we hope Turok & Boyle may have a paper on this at some stage, or at least might be prepared to discuss the close analogies with String Theory.)

Next, we’ve noted the spinor ψ is a transformation instruction, it has to be Bayesian updated as time marches forward (so to speak). The β factor in Eq.(3) could thus be taken to be also spacetime position-dependent, and this merely statistically accounts for the chance a photon from the future will “hit” the electron. The difficulty in handling Fock space with the Dirac spinor alone is here just a reminder that the spinor (wavefunction) time evolution is a fictional accounting tool, not suited for all purposes.

On the other hand, the need to reinterpret the Dirac spinor as an operator *acting on* a Fock space is also a good clue that ψ is an abstraction and an *instruction*, not a model for a fermion, which is in accord with our point of view.

³ It has to be this way for now because we do not have a way to experimentally test T4G theory.

In this overtly collisional process picture it becomes important that there is an ambient curved spacetime, since the probability that nearly point-like particles ever interact in purely spacetime physics is zero. The 4-geons are minimal Planck scale topology recall, they are not diffuse waves, we presume they do not have significant black-hole like horizons to capture photons easily without spacetime curvature. There has to be gravity, or at the bare minimum vacuum topology mediated processes.⁴

It seems remarkable that without any mathematics — most of this so far is just informal logic — we can motivate the existence of wormholes in spacetime. All we did was ask for radical minimalism consistent with known physics. However, it should not be construed as remarkable. None of this is feasible without all the history of physics. “Standing on the shoulders of giants,” does not even do the physicists of the past justice. They removed several dozens of pages of mathematics from this paper.

We now can show the wormhole structure implies generic indivisible T4G cobordisms. Furthermore, there is yet another logical way to do this. Due to our restrictions, there is *only one way* to account for entanglement in T4G, which is via ER-bridges. In §II.B we found entanglement implies an indivisible stochastic transition matrix. The bare bones ISQM is consistent with 4D spacetime kinematics, and so the generic T4G cobordism is indivisible.

The formal argument is as follows:

1. Entanglement is always due to wormhole-like connections (ER=EPR) in T4G context (our restricted context).
2. Generic real world systems have multiple entangling interactions.
3. Spacetime dynamics in the presence of ubiquitous wormhole topology cannot prevent information re-entering the system from the ‘past’ (in some foliation). (Nor indeed, in T4G theory, from the ‘future’!)

This assumption strongly suggests that the system is never truly isolated from some form of hidden degrees of freedom, meaning that the dynamics is fundamentally non-Markovian. Since Markovianity requires a loss of correlation with past states, but ER=EPR ensures persistent connections, we expect generic quantum stochastic processes to be indivisible.[37]

⁴ The concept of a *wormhole gas* ubiquitous in spacetime has been raised before.[36] Speculatively, this might also be related to either: (i) the dimension zero Bogoliubov scalars that are required in the CPT-Symmetric universe proposal.[32]; or (ii) the right-handed neutrino as the dark matter. Putting those two papers just cited together (with a chiral twist?) we get either the result the right-handed neutrino is an almost static wormhole gas, or that the Higgs mechanism is wormhole mediated.

The assumption the T4G cobordism has ER-bridge connections with the external spacetime can also probably be relaxed (if one cares to do so, though there is no reason to⁵). The requisite non-Markov stochastic dynamics can occur without information backflow if there is entanglement in the quantum part of the system.[37, 38]

We can perhaps go further. It is quite realistic that the T4G cobordism is always indivisible, but our measurements do not have to care about all that goes in spacetime, if only the particle processes that are not influenced by the wormhole entanglement structure are of relevance in a given experiment then it will look like a classical physics experiment. Appearances are usually *never* everything (except in elitist socialite circles). But appearances are everything *for our models* when appearances are our only grip on base reality.

III.D.3. What does indivisibility mean?

We have an unambiguous stochastic definition of indivisibility in Eq.(2). It is pleasing to provide a realist spacetime reason for this non-Markov stochasticity in our universe’s generic time evolution picture. Can we provide one?

The problem is that the T4G-cobordism in our experiments is not stochastic, it is a static tiny chunk of the 4D Block Universe. The electron (if it was an observer) “knew” it was going to get turned around in time. (Or The Cosmos knew, or whatever).

We thus need to “forget” we know the future and yet imagine ER-bridges nevertheless exist in the future and enter the T4G cobordism in-between measurement times. Admittedly this is a bit of mental torture, but it can be done, at least the forgetting the future part! It does provide a sufficient physical picture of T4G indivisibility. Perhaps it is not complete and sufficient to appeal to information back-flow into the cobordism to get indivisibility, this is at least a typical way the forgetful (hence stochastic) account of the transition from ∂M_1 to ∂M_2 is ISQM compliant.

None of this should be shocking. In orthodox QFT the indivisibility of the stochastic dynamics was already manifest. One way of reinterpreting our result is as a justification for the use of the apparatus of QFT. It answers the question *Where does QFT come from?* The answer is from spacetime topology. The new contribution here is that we no longer need to regard the fields as fundamental, the elementary particles (4-geons) are all we need together with a topologically non-trivial spacetime vacuum.

* * *

⁵ Any realistic physical system is always open.

Showing indivisible stochastic processes occur in the T4G cobordism is possibly all we need to establish T4G is a bona fide quantum theory. We would like to hear from experts who care about well-defined “quantum theories” — the axiomatic variety or the informal variety — if this is the case. There is more to T4G theory however, because it makes a stronger ontological claim about what goes on in-between two measurements, we have the additional burden of needing to show nothing in the T4G cobordism violates any known principles of physics.

This could be an entire research program, and is one motive for this paper — to stimulate T4G research, so to aid in this purpose we will now provide a few more sections on what could be done to establish T4G is consistent and yields a quantum theory.

III.E. Quantum Logic from T4G

It is possible to make this section redundant, because *if*, as we will show in §III.F, the generic T4G-cobordism yields an ISQM theory *then* the measurement proposition logic of QM is inherited. As we’ve been at pains to point out T4G theory is underdeveloped, and so a second way to see that T4G is a quantum theory could be useful for some students.⁶

A *quantum logic* for our purposes will be any physical proposal that has a non-distributive orthomodular lattice of measurement propositions [39].

Once we have a Quantum Logic (QL) then the minimal additional requirements we need for a “textbook” quantum mechanics [40] is:

Some form of continuity in the lattice structure.

From there, Solèr’s theorem [41] tells us the system can be modelled in a Hilbert space. We have this in T4G since we take our fundamental states to be multivectors in the STA. They describe continuous transformations on the (also STA) algebra of observables. Hence to obtain QM from T4G we only need QL.

Definition: a **measurement** is defined by a preparation of a bounded region of the manifold \mathcal{M} . Although “past” and “future” are frame dependent, for most typical experiments one frame is singled out as the *laboratory frame* and in this frame a clock is taken to define boundaries of the experiment, which are 3-manifolds $M^3(t_0) = \partial M_0$ and $M^3(t_1) = \partial M_1$ which are bordant (boundaries of the 4-manifold measurement region). Such boundaries are still artificial, but if we take equivalence classes of measurements they can be also defined (we assume) up to ‘irrelevant details not recorded’.

Definition: measurement boundaries. The ‘past’ boundary (relative to the laboratory frame) is where state preparation occurs. The ‘future’ boundary is where recording takes place.

By the axioms of T4G theory an elementary ‘particle’ is a 4-geon, and in any volume of 3-space a clean attempt to measure the presence of a particle will result in either a ‘true’ or ‘false’ value. Because T4G is a spacetime theory it follows that the result of a measurement for one of two mutually exclusive propositions must also be either ‘true’ or ‘false’.

Definition 1 (consistent measurement processes). *Denote by $\mathcal{M} = [M]$ the equivalence class of spacetime manifolds consistent with a given measurement process.*

Proposition 2 (CTC effects). *In a T4G theory closed timelike curves set non-redundant boundary conditions on the spacetime cobordism comprising the measurement process.*

The existence of closed timelike curves (CTCs) in T4G cobordisms means the record boundary will record a classical *distribution* of measurement results. This means if an identical state is prepared under identical conditions then precisely the same measurement records will not be obtained.

For the following we will consider generic incommensurate observables P, Q . Each will be restricted naturally or artificially) to take either one of two values, say P^+ or P^- (resp. Q^+ or Q^-). For example, for polarizers this is standard, but for position and momentum variables we could use a collimator or barrier to force a \pm result within some interval, say $+$ for within the interval, and $-$ if outside the interval. Or for example ‘ Q^+ ’=to the right of a barrier, ‘ Q^- ’=to the left of a barrier, were Q to be say a position record.

Proposition 3 (incompatible measurements). *Conjugate variables for a system cannot be simultaneously measured.*

The justification for this is that T4G is a spacetime theory, and so we simply cannot physically set-up an instrument for measuring two incommensurate properties on the one recording boundary ∂M_1 . This is not a mere experimental disturbance version of Heisenberg’s Uncertainty principle. It is a more fundamental limitation on measurement possibilities.

Proposition 4 (T4G orthocomplementarity). *Measurement propositions on T4G cobordisms have an orthocomplement lattice structure (exactly the same as quantum mechanics).*

For a proof we will need to show T4G propositions a, b , etc., concerning the generic measurements P and Q , which are incommensurate (postulate 3) satisfy:

1. have a partial order relation, \leq .
2. have a complement operation a^\perp : $(a^\perp)^\perp = a$.

⁶ for thawing out frozen paradigms.

FIG. 1. Partial ordering of T4G manifolds for the propositions P^+ , P^- , Q^+ , Q^- .

3. have a meet relation $a \wedge b$ such that $a \wedge a^\perp = \mathbf{0}$, and $a \wedge a = a$.
4. have a join relation \vee such that $a \vee a^\perp = \mathbf{1}$.
5. may not satisfy distributivity of \wedge over \vee , but do satisfy orthomodularity:

$$a \leq b \quad \Rightarrow \quad b = a \vee (b \wedge a^\perp) \quad (5)$$

The first four 1–4 are rather trivial to prove, and amount nearly to choosing good definitions which make them clear. They are also true in a classical boolean algebra. The following definitions and associated results establish these properties for T4G theory.

We need a partial order relation \leq on the set of propositions, and notions of complement and meet and join. These are defined in T4G theory in almost obvious ways.

Definition 5 (partial order). *Propositions for recordings on T4G manifolds satisfy partial ordering. The order relation will be $A \leq B$ precisely when a class of manifolds \mathcal{M} compatible with a B record also yield an A record.*

The schematic for the orderings is shown in Fig.1.

The result we need is to show (i) reflexivity, (ii) anti-symmetry, (iii) transitivity — which define a partial order.

Clearly any measurement record $P \leq P$, since a record of P is compatible with itself (just choose the same manifold) $P = P$ hence $P \leq P$ too.

(ii) Suppose $A \leq B$ and $B \leq A$, then that means a manifold can be found compatible with both A and B . However, the T4G manifolds are only defined up to their measurement record equivalence classes (Defn.1) so up to such equivalences $A = B$, since the records will always agree.

(iii) Suppose $A \leq B$ and $B \leq C$, then certainly any manifold compatible with C will be compatible with A . Hence $A \leq C$, as required. \square

Definition 6 (meet). *The \wedge relation $a \wedge b$ (also called the **meet**) of two propositions, is defined to be the “greatest lower bound” proposition for the set $\{a, b\}$. That is, $a \wedge b$ is the largest subset in the space of measurement propositions that is “less than or equal to” both a and b . Here we use the \leq relation for the space of propositions (i.e.,*

compatible manifolds, so that $a \leq b$ means the manifolds that realize b whenever a is realized).

It is true that either P^+ or P^- could be recorded, since by definition the T4G theory is realist, the variables that can be measured have real values, even if they were not recorded. (We will deal with Bell Inequalities later.)

Hence $(X^+ \vee X^-) \equiv \mathbf{1}$ in the above lattice, (for either of $X \in \{P, Q\}$).

Definition 7 (Complement operation). *The same T4G propositions have a natural complement operation $^\perp$, satisfying the meet (\wedge) relation.*

*This algebraic $^\perp$ operation is defined by the class of all the 4-manifolds inconsistent with a proposition being true. Recall the **meet** operation, $A \wedge B$ is defined to be the greatest lower (infimum) proposition that makes A and B both true.*

The result we need is that by the definition just given A^\perp is incompatible with A , hence $A \wedge A^\perp = \mathbf{0}$ is certainly minimal, as required. Also, since any measurement proposition is compatible with itself $A \wedge A = A$ holds since A is certainly the minimal proposition if A occurs.

It is clear that $(A^\perp)^\perp = A$ by considering co-manifolds, that is, complemented measurement propositions having a given truth value ($\mathbf{1}$ /resp. $\mathbf{0}$) correspond one-to-one with the relevant subclass of \mathcal{M} being compatible /resp. incompatible, which correspond to a class $[M]$ and the co-manifold class $[M^\perp]$, where for manifolds the complement class $[M^\perp]$ is the class or set of all 4-manifolds not in $[M]$.

Note: these results hold in particular for the special classes of measurements we defined, $\{P^+, P^-, Q^+, Q^-\}$, any of which could be substituted for the A or B above. But we wanted to define \wedge and \vee for the general case of any propositions, since in general $A \wedge B \neq \mathbf{0}$.

Definition 8 (Join operation). *The **join** of two propositions A, B , denoted $A \vee B$, is the minimal space spanned by the pair. This is the least upper bound (supremum) of $\{a, b\}$ in the space of propositions, under the partial ordering relation “ \leq ”.*

The associated result is that T4G propositions satisfy the join relation. The first part of the proof is that we need to show $A \vee A^\perp = \mathbf{1}$. By Defn 7 the complement A^\perp cannot occur on the same record boundary as A , but one or the other must occur. The rest of the result needed is in Result-9, we need orthomodularity.

We have now prepared the definitions and results needed for the main result, which is that T4G defines a quantum logic.

III.E.1. T4G Orthomodularity

The orthomodularity 5 is a bit more subtle, and is the critical one to focus upon since it is the only non-classical postulate in QL. Before we proceed it is worth remarking

FIG. 2. T4G manifold classes for the propositions P^+ , P^- , Q^+ , Q^- . (See Result-9)

that in *classical mechanics* one can formulate measurement propositions that also fail the distributive rule, but only when the measurements are at different moments in time, but that implies they would be on a different cobordism boundary, and so is an entirely frivolous matter.

Result 9. *Measurement propositions, such as those in our set $\{P^+, P^-, Q^+, Q^-\}$ satisfy orthomodularity (as defined above).*

We prove the result by cases, with the aid of the following manifold class diagram (Fig.2).

For propositions related by the scheme in Fig.2 orthomodularity holds trivially, since here, $A^+ \leq B^+$ means $A^+ = \mathbf{1}$ implies $B^+ = \mathbf{1}$, so while certainly $B^+ \wedge A^{+\perp} = \mathbf{0}$. it does not matter, since $\mathbf{0} \vee X = X$ for any X , in particular for A^+ , hence

$$B^+ = A \vee (B^+ \wedge A^{+\perp}) \quad \text{whenever } A = \mathbf{1}$$

hence $A^+ \leq B^+ \Rightarrow B^+ = A^+ \vee (B^+ \wedge A^{+\perp})$ as required.

The case for $A^- \leq B^-$ is similar.

For B^+ and B^- we do not have the ordering relation, neither for $A^- \not\leq B^+$.

Also $A^{+\perp} \not\leq B^+$ and $A^{+\perp} \not\leq B^-$ unless $A^{+\perp} \leq A^-$, but then transitivity of \leq can be used.

That only leaves $B^- \leq A^{+\perp}$. In this case the consequent would read,

$$B^- = A^{+\perp} \vee (B^- \wedge A^+)$$

but this follows from $B^- \leq A^{+\perp}$ as desired since $A^{+\perp} \vee \mathbf{0} = A^{+\perp}$ by the maximal spanning space in Defn.8. \square

Hadley [5] points out that all the finite state systems also satisfy the Modularity property:

$$a \leq c \quad \Rightarrow \quad a \vee (b \wedge c) = (a \vee b) \wedge c.$$

We have not yet shown T4G propositions form a Lattice but the remark here is that infinite state systems fail to satisfy modularity (or systems with infinite spectrum of eigenvalues in QM). Localizing 4-geons in space is such an instance where modularity fails.

Localization of a 4-geon will thus imply propositions which fail Modularity (see [42, pages 83-84] which apparently⁷ precludes a “nice definition” of probability and

this led von Neumann to abandon the Hilbert space structure for the formulation of QM. (He went on to explore operator algebra.)

It is interesting to ponder whether the failure to find a “nice probability” when Modularity fails has something deeper to do with the non-classical GPTs. It certainly is the case that a more restrictive axiom had to be found (which was *orthomodularity*) and perhaps no great wonder that it might be associated with the non-classical GPT structure underlying QM.

We now show the *orthocomplement postulate 5* is satisfied in T4G theory. It follows by considering the manifolds classes and their complements, which were defined by co-manifolds, in Defn.7. Let \mathcal{M}_A be the class of manifolds with record boundary consistent with A , and \mathcal{M}_B likewise for B .

Then $A \leq B$ implies $\mathcal{M}_A \subset \mathcal{M}_B$. By standard set relations we have $\mathcal{M}_B^\perp \subset \mathcal{M}_A^\perp$, where \perp here is set complementation, (not the proposition algebra orthocomplement). Although these 4-manifold classes are classes, the ZFC set relations can still be assumed to hold — or one can say the appropriate setting for this analysis could be category theory, where we do not need the concept of “Set” and can define \subset to be a morphism \rightarrow between our equivalence classes of manifolds.

Since $\mathcal{M}_B^\perp \rightarrow \mathcal{M}_A^\perp$ in this language and by Defn.1 this means B^\perp is necessarily consistent with A^\perp , by the definition of “ \leq ” in Defn.5 this implies $B^\perp \leq A^\perp$, as required. \square

III.E.2. Discussion of Propositions

Further properties can be shown but are omitted for brevity, for example the T4G measurement propositions do indeed form a *lattice* and satisfy *atomicity* — i.e., there are simple minimal propositions. These results can also be found in [5].

The main discussion point for student readers is that the formality of the above presentation could be bypassed with some intuition. The main non-classical *geometry* of the T4G theory is the presence of the ER-bridges, which are the only way to account for entanglement if given our self-imposed constraints. This gives sufficient imagery for the imagination to visualize how superpositions effectively occur. A single particle history can wind around spacetime up to what vacuum (or other) ER-bridge structure can permit. But these are only statistically effective superpositions, the full-blown ontic superposition of a wavefunction is not real in T4G theory, but statistically it is completely effective.

You might think this is fence-sitting on the ψ -ontic versus ψ -epistemic debate. Our attitude is that such philosophy is interesting, and could have been important, but ultimately not too important if we understand the underlying phenomena. Do superpositions truly occur in T4G? The answer is yes. But do they all occur all the time (everything all at once until ‘measured’)? then the

⁷ See the discussion here <https://iep.utm.edu/qu-logic/>.

answer is no!

It is this intuitive picture that should allow students to study T4G in more detail, a picture unavailable in standard accounts of QM.

We will consider Proposition 3 to be a postulate for now, but it is not strictly a quantum postulate, since it should follow from general relativity. We believe it is possible to raise this postulate to a derivation, because it is the structure of a spacetime cobordism in the presence of CTCs that implies incompatible variables. Recall that in classical mechanics everything is tied together nicely by phase space. So there are no incompatible observables in CM. There are only measurements that will never be made. They are impossible because they will not be time-evolved by the laws of motion. This is distinct to the QM & T4G situation.

This is, if you think about it, also the intuitive answer to the problem posed back on page 13 where we noted to obtain QM proper from QL one needed “*Some form of continuity in the lattice structure.*”

The empirical justification is well established, but we also think we have some theoretical underpinnings — namely in the Lie algebra structure for the spacetime symmetries. Where the Lie algebra generators, for say P and Q (any two incompatible observables) fail to commute then we cannot conserve both the currents associated with the two generators. In measurement theory terms, a recording of one of their eigenvalues, say P , will imply a greater than otherwise spread in eigenvalues for the other, Q .

Proposition 3 could thus use some elaboration, and we think it could be derived within a T4G framework. We will refrain in the present paper, but would like to point those interested in the problem to the basic idea. In our argument above we simply assert that P and Q happen to be incompatible. However, this does not show the orthodox QM observables are these P and Q pairs. To obtain orthodox QM we would need to prove no instrument can record such a pair simultaneously (hence on the one cobordism boundary ∂M_1). However, this is not too hard.

We only need to know that T4G measurements are described by STA projectors, similar to the projections in orthodox QM (in fact functorially equivalent) used to describe the measurement process outcomes, or the expectation values thereof. Thus, every *spacetime physics* measurement will be described by some STA multivector, say A , together with the action on that multivector by the spinor transform, $\psi A \tilde{\psi}$. (This could be considered the outcome from a hypothetical generic “simplest instrument” possible, in that it is the absolute physical limit on observation.) The rest of the argument is essentially the same as orthodox QM treatments, only here we have an explicit spacetime cobordism boundary account. The boundary ∂M_1 cannot possibly record data for both multivectors P and Q which form observables, and which fail to commute *in the STA*. The commutation relations from the STA are however, the same as in the orthodox

QM matrix formalism (which we now regard as an inferior framework). Thus our generic P and Q argument above will reproduce the Heisenberg incompatibility relations of orthodox QM.

* * *

We cannot help remarking that the Generalized Probability Theories (GPTs) offer perhaps an even simpler way to show T4G is a quantum theory, because the T4G-cobordism boundaries are equipped with measurement instruments and the spinor states ψ (from the STA). So we would only need the axiom of continuous transitions between states to single out the GPT for T4G theory as a quantum theory (i.e., having superposition and entanglement).[17] In the STA we do indeed have continuous transitions, but one would have to show these are *realized* in the T4G-cobordism. However, a theory that needs the existence of measurement instruments is perhaps not a fundamental theory of physics, and so this route to showing T4G is quantum mechanical is phenomenologically useful, but not our main interest.

A slightly more general way to derive QM from T4G would be to use the STA to get the Hilbert space via a GNS construction, see for example [43, Sec.4.5]. Pedagogically this could be the simpler approach, which we leave others to pursue starting from T4G fundamentals.

III.F. Realist Non-stochastic Interference

We have already seen that interference is guaranteed if the ISQM stochastic transitions are indivisible. While it would be very nice to demonstrate interference directly in a T4G-cobordism, we will take this more indirect approach of appealing to ISQM.

Our strategy is very simple. The spacetime in T4G is full of topological 4-geons, and hence full of wormhole-like structures. This derives from (1) the T4G particle postulate, and (2) the self-imposed minimalist restriction that nothing but 4D spacetime is permitted in the theory.

We then only need to show at least in T4G context, that existence of entanglement generically implies indivisibility. It then follows that the generic T4G cobordism exhibits interference.

III.F.1. Quantum channels in T4G cobordisms

Consider a *quantum channel*, which for our purposes is a mathematical description of how a quantum state evolves (or is transmitted) in a physical process, including the effects of noise and decoherence. Formally, it’s a map Λ that takes a density matrix ρ (representing a quantum state) to another density matrix $\rho' = \Lambda(\rho)$. They are (1) linear, (2) trace preserving, (3) completely positive (CP), that is, (i) takes any positive semidefinite density matrix to another positive semidefinite den-

sity matrix, and (ii) for any ancillary system (of arbitrary size) with the identity channel \mathbb{I} , the extended map $\mathbb{I} \otimes \Lambda$ also sends any joint (possibly entangled) state to another valid state. This guarantees that the quantum channel does not produce unphysical outcomes (like negative probabilities) even when the system is part of a larger entangled state.

We are using the theoretical constructs of CP maps because they simplify a guarantee that our evolution is physically valid even when entanglement is present. This provides a model for studying how quantum processes behave when they are “sliced” into pieces.

III.F.2. The Choi Isomorphism and CP Maps

Any quantum channel Λ acting on a system (or composite system) can be represented by its Choi state:

$$C_\Lambda = (\mathbb{I} \otimes \Lambda)(|\Phi\rangle\langle\Phi|),$$

where $|\Phi\rangle$ is a maximally entangled state on a doubled Hilbert space. A necessary and sufficient condition for Λ to be completely positive is that C_Λ is a positive semidefinite operator.

For a divisible process, we require that for any $t_2 > t_1$ there exists an intermediate CP map $\Lambda(t_2, t_1)$ such that

$$\Lambda(t_2) = \Lambda(t_2, t_1) \circ \Lambda(t_1).$$

By the Choi–Jamiołkowski isomorphism[44], the Choi state for the intermediate map $C_{\Lambda(t_2, t_1)}$ must be positive semidefinite (and in many cases, separable with respect to an appropriate partition).

Now, suppose we have a composite system AB with density matrix ρ_{AB} and its evolution is described by a stochastic transition matrix (or equivalently, a channel) $T_{AB}(t)$. If this matrix is entangled, it means that the corresponding Choi state $C_{T_{AB}(t)}$ is entangled, that is, it does not decompose as a convex sum of product states:

$$C_{T_{AB}(t)} \neq \sum_j p_j \rho_j^A \otimes \rho_j^B$$

In other words, the effective description of the evolution involves correlations between A and B that cannot be captured by independent (or even correlated via a separable process) CP maps acting on A and B separately.

To recapitulate the above more in ISQM terms, a divisible (Markovian) process allows us to break the overall channel $\Lambda(t)$ into intermediate CP maps:

$$\Lambda(t_2) = \Lambda(t_2, t_1) \circ \Lambda(t_1)$$

where each intermediate map $\Lambda(t_2, t_1)$ is CP. This is reminiscent of ISQM, and is really exactly the same concept.

If the Choi state of the overall channel shows entanglement, this indicates that when we try to “slice” the time evolution, the intermediate maps would fail to be CP —

they would have to “rebuild” the entanglement (or memory) between the parts. Thus, the process is indivisible (hence also non-Markovian).

There is a T4G cobordism picture for this. Imagine a spacetime cobordism defined by two measurement boundaries. The evolution from one boundary to the other is described by a quantum channel.

If this channel is divisible, the process is “memoryless,” and any entanglement generated by earlier interactions is lost. Conversely, if the channel is indivisible, its Choi state reveals entanglement between the boundaries. This entanglement is a signature that information (or correlations) flows back into the system. In a T4G picture this would correspond to ER-bridges that have an interior end and an end possible outside the T4G-cobordism region.

There is some work here for interested students. Can we regard the *quantum channel* context as universal for ISQM stochastic processes? In particular, can every T4G cobordism be functorially mapped to some quantum channel? For the present paper we are going to follow the intuition this is indeed the case, so leave it as a conjecture to prove later.

This completes the set-up for our result.

III.F.3. Indivisibility Follows from Entanglement

If the overall channel $T_{AB}(t)$ were divisible, that is, if we could write $T_{AB}(t) = T_{AB}(t, t_1) \circ T_{AB}(t_1)$ with $T_{AB}(t, t_1)$ being CP for every intermediate time t_1 , then the Choi state of the intermediate map, $C_{T_{AB}(t, t_1)}$, would necessarily be positive. When we combine CP maps, the overall process is effectively built from local (or at least CP) pieces.

However, if the effective transition matrix $T_{AB}(t)$ is entangled, it means that no matter how you try to slice the time evolution, the intermediate map would have to rebuild these entangled correlations. This forces the intermediate map to have a Choi state that cannot be written in the form required for CP maps. In technical terms, if one attempts to define

$$T_{AB}(t, t_1) = T_{AB}(t) \circ T_{AB}(t_1)^{-1}$$

one finds that $T_{AB}(t, t_1)$ would exhibit gains or negative contributions (e.g., negative decay rates when represented in a time-local master equation) that signal a violation of CP.

In other words, the presence of entanglement in the effective transition matrix means that the memory of the initial correlations is not lost but rather is essential for the evolution. This memory effect prevents the evolution from being cut into independent CP steps — thus, the overall process is indivisible.

III.F.4. Summary for T4G Indivisibility

We’ve shown that generically if the stochastic transition matrix (or channel) which governs the evolution of a composite quantum system is entangled, then the correlations encoded in that entanglement prevent the evolution from being split into independent, CP intermediate maps. In other words, entanglement in the transition matrix implies that there is a nontrivial memory or correlation between subsystems that cannot be erased by dividing the time evolution, hence, the process is indivisible (non-Markovian).

This argument is quite general and shows that the very structure of entangled transition matrices is incompatible with the existence of a CP-divisible (Markovian) decomposition. Because the generic T4G-cobordism contains ubiquitous entanglement structure (wormhole-like structures) this implies T4G is a quantum theory. Not merely quantum logic on the cobordism boundaries ∂M_1 and ∂M_2 but a full blown quantum theory which implies Schrödinger–Dirac time evolution for the *statistically effective* unitary stochastic ψ evolution.

III.G. The Standard Model from T4G?

T4G theory lends itself well to employing the Clifford algebra $Cl(3, 1)$, also called the Spacetime Algebra (STA) for the elementary particle representations, which we reviewed in §III.A.1. This is a real algebra (isomorphic to $M(\mathbb{R}, 4)$), with a “complex structure” imposed by several unit imaginaries, not just one, moreover each imaginary has a clear 4D spacetime geometric interpretation. The geometry for point locale frames is thus *real* and Minkowski, but the spacetime topology is **non-Minkowski**.

We know that the generators for $\mathfrak{su}(3)$, $\mathfrak{su}(2)$, $\mathfrak{u}(1)$, can be expressed in terms of the STA (see for example [6]). In this approach the Dirac spinors (and Majorana spinors) are represented by elements in the *even subalgebra* of $Cl(3, 1)$. All Standard Model fermions also have biquaternion representations[45] and biquaternions are also naturally represented by elements in the $Cl(3, 1)$, as can the twistors [46].

The elementary particles are not explicitly represented in this combined T4G+STA approach. Rather the spinors are clearly transformation instructions, acting on the spacetime observables (the Dirac bilinear invariants). These are sufficient for all measurement models in quantum physics, since all other observables can be written in terms of the bilinear invariants.

The papers just cited are not yet a full account of the Standard Model but they are promising.

III.G.1. Bipartite Structure but No Uninterpreted \mathbb{C} Numbers

Although the \mathbb{C} numbers arise naturally from stochastic processes in ISQM when one demands time evolution of the amplitudes (the roots of the entries in the Γ) there is no need to take these particular complex numbers too seriously, since the Hilbert space is a fictional accounting tool.

Whereas in the STA (hence inherited by T4G) the rotor and pseudoscalar in Eq.(3) give us unavoidable bivector and hence complex structure, but in real-valued spacetime. The Lorentzian path integral in QFT also follows from the bivector structure of the Dirac Theory, since the Lagrangian can be constructed from the spinor theory. What is remarkable here is that the interference terms arise naturally from the bivector and pseudoscalar “complex” structures in the spinor theory. It is classical mechanics which artificially suppresses this natural structure in geometric physics – by discarding all but the path of least action. That is the sensible thing to do of course, if one had no evidence for entanglement or spacetime cobordism indivisibility or equivalent phenomena.

In other words, T4G theory inherits the geometric spacetime interpretation of all the “complex” structure in orthodox QM, with one possible interesting exception (which may in any case prove the rule). This exception is for $\mathfrak{su}(3)$ which in the STA appears by most accounts to require a bipartite structure (see [47, 48]). In [6] Lasenby seeks to avoid an explicit uninterpreted unit imaginary by using an ordered pair structure. We suggest this is an algebraic way of “hiding” — or maybe mimicking is the better term — wormhole topology. If our hunch is correct then no uninterpreted unit imaginary is needed in fundamental physics including the entire Standard Model as we know it today.

III.G.2. A T4G Holography-like Challenge

We pose a challenge that it is surely no coincidence that (apart from more exotic GHZ states⁸), (i) a quantum theory only has algebraic bipartite structure (which we are claiming is for the two ends or connection points of wormhole Planck structure), and (ii) QM is a measurement theory well-defined only at boundaries. If the quantum theory is describing only boundaries then it cares not what goes across the ER-bridges. That is a Planck microcosm so-to-speak for the entire T4G-cobordism.

Related to the last remark, on a more philosophical aside, we feel that a lot of barriers to completing quantum mechanics are erected because of the fact QM inherently

⁸ The GHZ states do not make things any *more quantum* nor any *less quantum*, since the wormhole topology in these cases is not bipartite (not monogamous).

focuses on the measurement boundaries ∂M_1 and ∂M_2 of the spacetime cobordism. The full geometry is not on the submanifold boundary, but is in the bulk gravity. The quantum theory on the other hand only needs to be concerned with these boundaries. This should be reminiscent of gauge-gravity duality (the AdS/CFT playground). The T4G-cobordism could be seen as a “mini” bulk-boundary holography theory,⁹ but with leaky interior, hence irreducibly stochastic if the physical description is restricted to the light cones.

III.H. Open Questions for T4G

We find it convenient to use the phrase *Minkowski lens* to refer to the point of view one proverbially ‘sees’ if viewing the world through the lens of flat trivial spacetime. If wormholes exist, in other words, one is blind to them if using the Minkowski lens.

We hesitate to say T4G is a theory. It is a speculative proposal for a basis for unifying general relativity and quantum mechanics, but by asking each of these great theories to abandon a couple of orthodox notions. For GR we abandon everywhere local Minkowski topology, since over a large enough region in any cobordism between two closed compact submanifold boundaries of spacetime (a “laboratory experiment”) we suppose traversable wormholes can be found. These are not classically traversable though, only qubits can traverse the T4G wormholes, since they are minimal.

For QM we abandon the notion that entanglement is holographic, and instead the bulk gravity is real and the wormhole structure *is* entanglement structure. We are thus inverting the current AdS/CFT paradigm. We regard the bulk as fundamental, and the boundary as merely asymptotic. This is more in accord with our actual FRWL cosmos, so we feel this inversion of mainstream thought is justified.

We thus also rephrase the ER=EPR koan, it becomes ER \Rightarrow EPR, and GR+CTCs \Rightarrow QM. We emphasize the T4G ER-bridge is still “highly quantum” [49] however T4G theory has a clear conception of what this means. Gharibyan showed that the geometrical notion of entropy associated with an ER-bridge satisfies the same inequalities as entanglement entropy. Both ER-bridges and entangled states also forbid faster-than-light signalling (in the wormhole case it is due to *topological censorship* theorems which arise from weak energy conditions [50]). Hence neither entropy considerations nor traversability mark a Planck scale T4G wormhole as distinctly ‘quantum.’ Conventionally what “highly quantum” means is that a black hole formed from entangled states could be (in principle) formed from GHZ states, not classical wormholes.

One might whimsically say this is *Non-locality without Non-locality*, since through the wormhole qubits can propagate locally at light speed, but from the external Minkowski lens this will appear non-local. However, the wormholes in T4G are minimal, so cannot support macroscopic traversals. This is well known in GR: macroscopic matter (or energetic enough photons) probing a GR wormhole collapses the wormhole (see, [51–53]). We should note in passing the null energy condition violations needed for stable wormholes imply inherent instability for macroscopic (non-Planckian) wormholes. An independent argument can be made from an AdS/CFT context the wormhole is inherently unstable since it is dual to entanglement, hence when entanglement is ‘broken’ by any sufficiently ‘violent’ measurement the wormhole collapses. There is no reason to think the same would not hold for actual (non-holographic) Planck scale wormholes in FRWL bulk.

In any case, the T4G picture of a T4G-cobordism provides a holographic microcosm, with the bordant boundaries where the “CFT” theory is defined, and the cobordism interior the gravity bulk. It might even be mathematically plausible to show that this CFT-like boundary holography is actually Standard Model QFT — since we’d be removing the toy-like notion of AdS. We pose the question: exactly what is dual to a T4G-boundary set of data?

Although T4G does not depart from orthodox QM for measurement processes, nonetheless, T4G is different. In this respect T4G theory is consistent with ISQM, because T4G proposes to *provide* the ontological structure for the spacetime cobordism that ISQM requires. This presumes the hope is to make ISQM founded upon spacetime physics. T4G is different, because it makes a strong ontological claim about the spacetime physics that gives rise to QM. T4G goes beyond the mere measurement theory framing of QM. Thus T4G can be tested.

Put another way, QM only concerns us with the boundaries, ∂M , of the ST-cobordism. The measurement preparation and detection events in other words. T4G says something about the cobordism interior.

A true test of T4G would require directly probing this Planck scale topology — a very difficult task for experimental physics. However there may be indirect tests. In the following paragraphs we will remark on a few possibilities.

The way classical physics emerges is clear in T4G, and there are probably ways to derive Tsirelson bounds. This is because all quantum effects in T4G theory arise from the wormhole or ER=EPR structure.

The ER-bridge structure might be a way to test T4G. However, there seems no immediate distinction between ER and EPR, as earlier mentioned [49]. While ER-bridges also forbid faster-than-light signalling between external observers, they do not prevent *quantum information* traversal (which is why teleportation protocols are possible). This is information that is not classically communicated, and hence does not collapse the ER-

⁹ Not as a mini cosmology, but just a mundane mini holography tiny sub-universe, so-to-speak.

bridge (equivalently break entanglement). T4G theory does require traversable ER-bridges in order to account for superposition and hence also interference. Our abstract arguments based on ISQM suggest logically this is not a problem for T4G theory, but it would be nice to have a purely spacetime topology account for the effective superpositions. If such an account were possible it might be used in sensitive tests that can non-invasively probe the ER-bridge structure. Or one could take a converse route: if one could prove statistically effective superposition cannot possibly arise from ER-bridge quantum information traversals then this would be a significant discredit for T4G theory, almost a no-go result. It would imply our previous logic was faulty, which would be a significant result in itself, since the only assumption which seems reasonably disputable would also effect ISQM, which was (§III.F) that “existence of entanglement generically implies indivisibility.”

An interesting conceptual issue, similar to the problem of the Feynman vertex in non-stringy QFTs, is how interactions are even possible if 4-geon wormhole ends are essentially minimal black hole regions? When would they ever get close enough for spacetime topology change to occur? The T4G intuition is that spacetime curvature eventually becomes important on the small scale, but also the vacuum is riddled with ‘wormhole gas’ structure, and this is what mediates 4-geon interactions. These conceptual speculations invite theoretical research to fill-in this philosophical gap. It would be an even greater advance if such issues of vertex interactions could be experimentally probed. We do not know of any such viable methods. The carrot here is that clearly there is some scope for understanding the coupling constants.

Closely related to the previous is the fact the graviton does not change particle quantum numbers, which is easily understood in T4G theory since the graviton in T4G is not topological, it is just the gravity wave. This explains why the gravity gauge fields are pure holonomy, they are not associated with local compact Lie symmetries (so-called ‘internal’ symmetries, which in T4G context are all manifestations of *local* non-trivial spacetime topology). Applying only a *Minkowski lens* one ‘sees’ no such topology and hence is forced into contrivances like gauge fibres “living on spacetime.”

III.H.1. Spin Measurements

The Stern-Gerlach experiment is not a discrete spin effect according to T4G, it is a polarization effect, which many physics textbooks have ignored. There is a quantum torque term in the full Dirac theory treatment of the electron, which polarizes an initially homogeneous electron beam of particles. [54, 55] This suggests that if tests can be found which invalidate the polarization interpretation of Stern-Gerlach filters, then it would go a long way towards invalidating T4G theory. Intrinsic spin in T4G is of course nothing more than the fact the clas-

sical rotors for geometric algebra are algebraically unit ‘fermions’ (elements of the even subalgebra of spacetime [56] — an entirely classical notion) and thus in the fundamental representation for $SU(2)$.

III.H.2. Wave-particle Duality

While we are not aware of tests of wave-particle duality, T4G is a pure particle theory, the fields are fictional accounting tools, as was (we believe) always supposed by Feynman. This may open up room for subtle tests. At stake here is the myth of “wave-particle duality.” Is this myth just lore or is it law? We count it one of the great unsolved problems in philosophy of quantum physics.

III.H.3. Decoherence

Decoherence is a spacetime physics effect in T4G. But it does not require the Penrose-Diósi mechanism, nor the GRW mechanism. For large systems entanglement simply plays less of a statistically significant role. Since entanglement in T4G is ER-bridge structure, there is no metaphysical postulate that all things are subject always to entanglement. In the ISQM framework the compatible but weaker statement is that when the cobordism becomes divisible then there is no significant entanglement (or any entanglement is being ignored in the experiment).

A far back as 2018, Joseph Samuel [57] was proposing a more banal argument for why gravity should cause decoherence. Here with T4G theory we are saying that *only* gravity causes decoherence, since all interactions are gravitational, just not all classical (holonomy), the critical interactions are topological.

III.H.4. Tunnelling

Quantum tunnelling should be another sensitive place to test T4G. The idea is that there is no real wave, so the tunnelling is mediated by the wormhole structure, and thus is an inherently non-local effect again when seen from the Minkowski lens (though completely local at the Planck scale). It is easy conceptually to imagine how spacetime wormhole structure can tunnel electrons or photons, but much harder to conceive of the far greater coincidences of wormhole traversals needed to tunnel a whole atom.[58, 59] Much like ultracold Bose-Einstein condensates, these whole atom tunnelling experiments are an incredible achievement of human civilization, and perhaps unique phenomena in our galaxy, hence the extreme engineering going in to producing these observations warrants some hope that the T4G-cobordism proposal for all quantum effects could get the tunnelling rates within empirical bounds. However, since T4G reproduces QM for single particles it seems uncontroversial

to have such hope, the harder work is to extend T4G theory to many-particle systems where all quantum effects must essentially be accounted for by mostly just bipartite entanglement.

We do not presently see any feasible way to compute whole atom tunnelling rates from T4G alone, we'd just end up reinventing QFT, or appealing to ISQM for non-relativistic particles.

III.H.5. Gravitational Two-slits

Another area where there could be obvious tests would be in gravitational two-slit experiments (the Aharonov–Feynman effect), or more sensitive spin-entanglement witnesses for purely gravity mediated entanglement [60] which purport to be tests for existence of gravitons, which T4G has a more nuanced view of — specifically that gravitons do not exist except as gravitational waves that are entangled somehow. However, in T4G the gravity waves are not topological, so should not be entangled in the same way as fermions or SM bosons, and so quantum gravity effects are predicted by T4G theory to be far more subtle, and derivative (so-to-speak) of actual entanglement of the matter particles and *perhaps more importantly the vacuum*. Hence gravitational interference ought to be possible to generate, but might be extremely difficult to cleanly observe. It is subtle because gravity in T4G is not classical, but is also not a Yang–Mills force, and the gravity waves will interfere, since they *are* waves.

How are we to ever experimentally distinguish a hypothetical *single* graviton interference effect from a mere gravity wave? This is a challenge most so-called ‘entanglement witnesses for gravity’ experimentalists seem to not even be considering.

A cleaner test of T4G would need to be experimental evidence the actual spacetime metric exists in superposition. We know of no such experimental proposals. The spin-witness proposals only check for gravity mediated entanglement, and if found would be compatible with T4G. In addition T4G theory presumes “the metric” is unphysical, as in orthodox GR. (We only ever directly detect energy deposition, not “distance”.)

No direct T4G research is being done in this field that we know of, but the *post-quantum gravity* research program [61] could be also compatible with T4G, since in their work the Aharonov–Feynman effect is predicted to be washed-out (unobservable) due to stochastic gravity. This is (almost?) nothing but a synthesis of ISQM and classical GR, so is compatible with T4G theory, although even here there should be subtle differences since in T4G gravity is strictly speaking not classical although there is no graviton. In TG4 theory the entire Standard Model of particle physics *is* gravity, but is the homotopy of spacetime rather than the holonomy (GR).

III.H.6. Entanglement Structures

A pure spacetime account of the EPRB experiments was given in a companion preprint [62]. Without direct probes of Planck scale structure we cannot of course make any strong claims. All that this T4G–EPR preprint can say is that *if* there is some kind of harmonic oscillation (wormhole gravity wave?) along the T4G wormhole structures, then it *could* account for the EPRB correlations, locally and realist. The non-locality is because if one is blind to non-trivial spacetime topology then one has to conclude there is non-local correlation relative to your (fictitious) Minkowski frame. T4G is not everywhere locally Minkowski, except on some kind of smoothed average, hence T4G can be local-realist QM, and what we abandon is the notion of spacetime being everywhere locally Minkowski.

Entanglement probing is thus another test area for T4G theory. GHZ states are not apparently explicable in terms of classical GR wormholes [27, 49], which seems to strongly imply fundamental restrictions on the scale and extent of quantum entanglement conceived as real Planck-scale wormhole topology. In particular classical ER=EPR states are monogamous and cannot account for GHZ states. Thus general entanglement has a degree of non-monogamy and so the topology cannot be the classical type of wormhole topology. How to probe such theoretical considerations remains an open challenge. How to formulate a contradiction is the theoretical problem here. If the GHZ states are still explicable via exotic spacetime topology then it could be difficult to force a contradiction. Our best guess would be in the time-domain, to look for theoretical constraints on stability and persistence perhaps. It is only a suggestion, but perhaps T4G theory could derive lifetimes for GHZ states? If ‘quantum entanglement’ is more *metaphysical* and not due to spacetime topology there should be no limit to the lifetime of GHZ states, if some sort of quantum Zeno effect was imposed. This would then become a good test.

* * *

Although we’ve not supplied an exhaustive list of tests, one other worth mentioning is in gravitational wave detection. Recent modelling by Nadi et al [63] suggest ways *gravity induced entanglement* (GIE) might be detectable. There are two subtleties for a T4G analysis here: one is that we would say all entanglement is already gravitational, so we would not use the phrase “gravitationally induced entanglement,” since that is a redundant phrase. A more important subtlety is that naïve T4G theory would suggest gravity waves are not graviton fields, rather the gauge gravity fields are just mathematical transforms, as in Gauge Theory Gravity (classical) [64] and they do not need quantization rules, since they are not topological particles — the gravity waves have trivial topology. This in turn strongly suggests gravity waves themselves cannot be entangled, since according

to T4G, at least naïvely, all entanglement involves non-trivial spacetime topology (wormholes).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Any generic spacetime T4G-cobordism (a bulk-like sub-region of spacetime) has a stochastic transition matrix account, which is concerned only with two measurement boundaries. Using Barandes’ ISQM framework we showed a generic T4G-cobordism containing ubiquitous Planck scale wormhole-like structures is indivisible, we have thus shown T4G theory is at least a variety of quantum theory, and contains orthodox QM.

Exploiting the Spacetime Algebra (STA) we have clues that 4D spacetime contains rich enough algebraic topology to account for the full LR-Symmetric Standard Model (SM). The SM *physical*-geometric fermions are however not geometrically spinors, the spinors are only representations of transformations on the multivector observables in the same algebra. If the elementary particles are topological 4-geons their precise 4D topology remains unknown, but algebraic topology should have something coarse to say about the 4-geons, if they exist, by using the Lie groups of the SM as hints about the homotopy or homological structure.

Several quintessentially quantum phenomena should have departures when analyzed from a gross QFT calculation compared to a T4G simulation. Because T4G reproduces orthodox QM for single particles, these tests would be at either the quantum/classical boundary or the Planck scale. As tunnelling, decoherence, and gravitational two-slit experiments become better empirically understood there are viable testing grounds for T4G. Most such tests seem to be viable as almost “desktop physics.” (A quantum computer is a pretty good laboratory.)

We have not proposed any changes in basic physics in this paper. Some of the proposed tests could reveal de-

partures from orthodox QFT but because experiments are nowhere near such limits of QFT — and are all practically in the realm of so-called “quantum gravity” — we can be confident no essential physics is getting modified in our approach, which we regard as just a fresh mathematical perspective on quantum physics.

There is a remark also to be made concerning sociology of physics. T4G theory is entirely unknown in mainstream discourse, and so there is ample scope in the short term for graduate level research and harvesting of many low-hanging fruit. In addition, the clean 4D spacetime picture of quantum mechanics should be very appealing to teachers. An undergraduate course might be able to reach the basics of the Path Integral formulation and early QFT in a few semesters, without appealing to the abstractions of Hilbert spaces and operator algebras. The teacher could start with spacetime physics, stick to the STA and rapidly develop a pedagogical route to the path integral without any metaphysical speculation on “the meaning of it all,” since on the supposition T4G theory is correct to some degree we hope we have shown there is nothing “weird” that remains in quantum theory.

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One of us¹⁰ (BS) has been exploring topological 4-geon theory since the mid 1990’s before Mark Hadley published his thesis, but unfunded and with no collaborators and no confidence. This present paper would not have been posted without the inspiration from Neil Turok and Latham Boyle [65–67] who have in principle solved a whole slew of major puzzles in fundamental physics with their LR-Symmetric Standard Model and CPT-Symmetric Big Bang proposals. All they did was take 4D spacetime seriously, and sought to find what they could squeeze out of a Minimalist program.

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¹⁰ There were supposed to be two authors, and I’ve resisted the urge to name the family cat as one. No animals were harmed in the production.

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